

Assessing Children’s Probabilistic and Creative Thinking in a Non-Formal Learning Context

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Abstract—Daily, we face unpredictable events, often attributed to chance, as there is no justification for such an occurrence. Chance, understood as a source of uncertainty, is present in several aspects of human life, such as weather forecasts, dice rolling, and lottery. Surprisingly, humans and some animals can quickly adjust their behavior to handle efficiently doubly stochastic processes (random events with two layers of randomness, like unpredictable weather affecting dice rolling). This adjustment ability suggests that the human brain has built-in mechanisms for perceiving, understanding, and responding to simple probabilities. It also explains why current trends in mathematics education include probability concepts in official curriculum programs, starting from the third year of primary education. In the first years of schooling, children learn to use a certain type of (specific) vocabulary such as: never, always, rarely, perhaps, likely, and unlikely, to help them to perceive and understand the probability of some events. These are keywords of crucial importance for their perception and understanding of probabilities. The development of the probabilistic concepts comes from facts and cause-effect sequences resulting from the subject’s actions, as well as the notion of chance and intuitive estimates based on everyday experiences. As part of a junior summer school program, which took place at a Portuguese university, a non-formal learning experiment was carried out with 18 children in the 5th and 6th grades. This experience was designed to be implemented in a dynamic of a serious ice-breaking game, to assess their levels of probabilistic, critical, and creative thinking in understanding impossible, certain, equally probable, likely, and unlikely events, and, also, to gain insight into how the non-formal learning context influenced their achievements. The criteria used to evaluate probabilistic thinking included: the creative ability to conceive events classified in the specified categories, the ability to properly justify the categorization, the ability to critically assess the events classified by other children, and the ability to make predictions based on a given probability.

Keywords—Critical and creative thinking, non-formal mathematics learning, probabilistic thinking, serious game.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNCERTAIN events are part of our everyday experience. These events are typically linked to the intuitive notion of chance, as they lack an evident rational explanation. People tend to perceive uncertainty in events as either theoretically knowable (*epistemic uncertainty*), inherently random (*aleatory uncertainty*) or a blend of both [1]. When faced with uncertainty, we must consider what to believe and also the strength we put into those beliefs. Because expectations often drive actions, determining appropriate degrees of belief is essential for making rational decisions. Determining an

appropriate and robust belief is critical for a wide range of decisions for both beginners and experts. A key concept in this process is associated with cases in which probabilistic beliefs approach absolute certainty (0 or 1). Judgment extremity influences the ability to discriminate between events and provides a framework for understanding the informational content of probabilistic assessments. Tannenbaum et al. [1] explored the influence of epistemic uncertainty, arising from incomplete knowledge about potentially knowable events, and aleatory uncertainty, arising from the inherent randomness of events, on judgment extremity. Their findings revealed a consistent tendency for judgments to become more extreme when the events are perceived as predominantly epistemic and less extreme when viewed as essentially aleatory.

In mathematics education, probabilistic reasoning, which begins in the third year of elementary school, plays a critical role. At this early stage, students are introduced to a specialized vocabulary, such as “always”, “never”, “likely”, “unlikely”, and “maybe”, to help them to discriminate and understand probabilistic events. These linguistic tools are essential for allowing children to classify events, make intuitive predictions, and begin to build a foundation for probabilistic reasoning. The development of probabilistic thinking depends heavily on the interaction between direct experiences, the recognition of cause-and-effect relationships, and intuitive judgments based on everyday observations. This set of cognitive skills is crucial for understanding uncertainty and serves as a gateway to higher-order critical and creative thinking.

In [2], Hoemann and Ros describe a research study on the development of children’s understanding of chance and probability, concluding that this occurs progressively through distinct cognitive stages, strongly influenced by their experiences, logical reasoning skills, and linguistic competence. They report that initially, children show immature reasoning, such as making predictions based on personal preferences or arbitrary associations. However, with exposure and cognitive growth, they begin to incorporate probabilistic reasoning, recognizing ratios and distributions in their predictions. This progression highlights the interdependence between cognitive development and the ability to understand and articulate probabilistic concepts. The findings further reveal that individual variations in acquiring and refining these concepts are shaped by several factors such as formal education, task complexity, and prior reinforcement experiences. The study also enhances the significance of

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structured interventions and targeted training programs in promoting children's probabilistic reasoning abilities.

The advancement of probability education, as mentioned by Batanero, and Álvarez-Arroyo [3], has been profoundly shaped by two key fields: statistics and mathematics education. Within the field of statistics, initiatives such as the International Conferences on Teaching Statistics (ICOTS), initially organized by the International Statistical Institute and later by the International Association for Statistical Education, highlighted the challenges faced by university-level statistics educators. Mathematics education, the unique branch of mathematics explicitly addressing uncertainty, highlights the need for research into the teaching and learning processes in this scientific area; the development of educational resources, and the design of teacher training programs.

Probability education has been a fertile area of investigation, attracting the attention of numerous researchers dedicated to advancing its theoretical foundations, pedagogical approaches, and practical applications. Scholars, such as Batanero et al. [4], Batista and Henriques [5], Kazak and Leavy [6], Leavy et al. [7], and Chernoff and Sriraman [8], have made significant contributions to the field through their comprehensive studies and publications. These works explore diverse aspects of probability education, from conceptual understanding and teaching strategies to curriculum development and teacher training.

Through the collective efforts of these researchers and organizations such as those mentioned above, probability education has evolved to align with the growing demands for statistical and probabilistic literacy in modern society.

Given the importance of fostering probabilistic thinking, especially in early education, innovative teaching methodologies are required to supplement traditional classroom practices. Non-formal learning environments offer unique opportunities for this purpose, providing dynamic and engaging contexts where abstract concepts can be explored interactively. To investigate this potential, a non-formal learning experiment was conducted as part of a junior summer school program at a Portuguese university. The study involved 18 children in the 5th and 6th grades and a serious game dynamic to assess their probabilistic, critical, and creative thinking. The aims of the study are threefold: to investigate children's understanding of concepts such as impossible, certain, (more/less/equally) likely, events; assess the ability to classify these types of events and provide reasoned justifications; and evaluate their ability to critically analyze the arguments for and against those made by their peers. To achieve these goals, we conducted a qualitative study with an interpretive focus, collecting data from students' written responses and detailed field notes kept by the researchers. This methodology allowed a differentiated analysis of children's cognitive processes, providing valuable insights into their conceptual understanding and reasoning skills. The findings suggest that integrating non-formal learning strategies such as serious games provide an effective and engaging method for improving students' probabilistic reasoning. Furthermore, this approach promotes the development of critical and creative thinking, enriching the overall learning

experience.

II. NON-FORMAL CONTEXTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROBABILISTIC THINKING

A. Probabilistic Thinking Through Non-Formal Learning

Using non-formal contexts to foster probabilistic thinking among children aged 10 to 13 years offers several significant advantages, addressing cognitive and affective dimensions of learning. This learning approach uses engaging, practical, and contextually relevant activities to increase understanding and applications of probabilistic concepts, fostering a genuine desire to explore the subject further [9], [10]. Non-formal contexts are often more effective than passive learning in formal settings, enabling students to uncover patterns and relationships through firsthand experiences [11], [12]. By confronting real-world situations involving probability concepts, children develop critical cognitive skills. Analyzing probabilistic learning scenarios and making informed decisions allows them to improve critical and logical reasoning.

Students are more likely to transfer their knowledge to new and unfamiliar situations, facilitating long-term retention and application, in non-formal learning contexts, which frequently involve group work, fostering collaboration, and communication skills, and increasing children's confidence, [13]-[15]. This double focus on social interaction and personal growth creates a long-lasting knowledgeable learning experience.

B. Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory

David Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, developed in the 1970s, builds upon the foundational work of several key thinkers in psychology and education. It draws inspiration from John Dewey's emphasis on the role of experience in education, Kurt Lewin's studies on experiential learning and group dynamics, and Jean Piaget's theories on cognitive development. Kolb synthesized these ideas to propose a cyclical learning model, emphasizing that knowledge is not merely acquired but actively constructed and transformed through critical experiential processes [16].

Kolb formally introduced this model defining four sequential stages for forming a continuous learning cycle: *concrete experience*; *reflective observation*; *abstract conceptualization*, and *active experimentation*. In the first phase of Kolb's learning cycle, *concrete experience*, individuals directly engage in an activity or situation, experiencing it practically and immediately. Concrete experience is the foundation upon which the entire learning process develops. After the concrete experience, the next phase is *reflective observation*. In this stage, individuals reflect on their experience, analyzing what happened and how they felt. Reflection allows people to process the experience more deeply, identifying patterns, problems, and learning opportunities. The third phase is *abstract conceptualization*. Here, individuals form abstract concepts and theories based on the reflections made in the previous phase. They generalize their observations and create mental models that can be applied to other situations.

The final phase of the cycle is *active experimentation*. In this stage, individuals apply the concepts and theories developed in the abstract conceptualization phase to new situations. They test their ideas in practice, adjusting and refining their approaches based on the results obtained.

Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory has applications in various contexts, including education, and personal development, [17], [18]. In educational settings, educators can structure activities that involve all four phases of the cycle, ensuring that students not only experience new situations but also reflect on them, form abstract concepts, applying them to new situations.

It offers a holistic and dynamic view of the learning process, emphasizing the importance of concrete experience, reflection, conceptualization, and experimentation, enhancing cognitive, social, and emotional skills, and developing a deeper and more enduring understanding of the world around them.

III. METHODOLOGY

Here, we report an exploratory research study on the development of probabilistic thinking in children, in a non-formal learning context. This study involved 18 children aged 10-13 years, all attending the 5th and 6th grades of basic education, enrolled in a one-hour session of a Summer School program at a Portuguese University. The main objective was to gain insights into how children understand key probabilistic concepts such as "impossible", "certain", "likely", "equally likely", and "unlikely" events, assessing their ability to classify these events and justify their reasoning.

A qualitative research approach with an interpretive focus was adopted from [19] and [20]. Data confidentiality was guaranteed and students' anonymity was maintained, with access to collected data restricted exclusively to researchers. The main instrument of analysis was a serious game designed specifically for this purpose. The game, central to the study design, was developed to engage children in dynamic and interactive scenarios that allowed them to explore probabilistic concepts, classify events, explain their reasoning, and engage them in critical discussions about the contributions of their peers.

Grounded in Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, this study adopted a qualitative approach with an interpretive focus. Kolb's model emphasizes learning as a cyclical process involving concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. These phases were integrated into the study design to foster deep learning and engagement with probabilistic concepts.

A. Concrete Experience

The session was held in a room equipped with round tables, see Fig. 1, creating an ideal setting for collaborative group activities. The children were invited to form groups of four or five members, which unfolded naturally and harmoniously, with each group sitting around one of the tables.

Once the groups were established, the session began with one of the two participant researchers engaging the children in a dialogue to ensure a clear understanding of the event's

probabilistic concept. Following this introduction, the children were tasked to provide examples to illustrate the concepts of impossible, certain, (more/less) likely, equally likely, and unlikely events.

Fig. 1 Learning and Creating Together: Summer School

Each child actively contributed by presenting their examples and offering their justifications. This was followed by a group discussion, where peers evaluated the validity of the given examples and arguments. This interactive approach fostered peer-to-peer engagement, encouraged critical thinking, and promoted collaborative learning, making the session dynamic and instructional.

B. Reflective Observation

Building on the peer-to-peer discussion, the children engaged in a hands-on activity to consolidate their understanding. The next task consisted of creating a paper fortune teller, following the step-by-step instructions in the YouTube video "How to Make a Paper Fortune Teller" [21]. Each participant created his own paper Fortune Teller. Once constructed, the upper faces were randomly numbered from 1 to 8, reinforcing the element of randomness in probabilistic reasoning, see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Paper Fortune Teller

Subsequently, the children were provided with a worksheet, the "Event Sheet" (Fig. 3), to collaboratively create and classify two "impossible," two "certain," two "(more/less/equal) likely,"

and two "unlikely" events. The groups were, then, instructed to randomly assign to each of these events, a number from 1 to 8, recording their selections on the "Event Sheet," see Fig. 3. This collaborative process encourages reflection, as the children

compare their reasoning with their group mates. It also promotes critical and creative thinking in a hands-on, agreeable manner.

Fig. 3 Probabilistic event recording

C. Abstract Conceptualization

The core activity of the study was a serious game designed to deepen the children's engagement with probabilistic thinking. The game encouraged abstract reasoning by requiring participants to classify probabilistic events while justifying their decisions.

Before the game begins, each group must select a leader whose role is to record, on the "Game Sheet", the points his/her team scores on each play.

All participants, except for the leaders, stand up in a circle, each equipped with his/her fortune-teller creation. The game follows a set of structured rules, namely:

1. *Starting the Game:* A player is randomly chosen to begin.
2. *Gameplay Mechanics:* The chosen player throws the ball to an opposing team member. Upon receiving the ball, the thrower asks the recipient, "How many do you want?" Then he uses his/her *Fortune Teller* to count out the chosen number, revealing four displayed numbers for the recipient to opt for one of them. The thrower, then, reads the event, written in his group's "Event Sheet", corresponding to the chosen number, and the receiver must classify it. Scoring is determined by Rule 3.
3. *Scoring System:* Each team starts with 20 points. Correct classifications add 2 points to the team's score, while incorrect classifications deduct 2 points.
4. *Play Continuation:* The player holding the ball throws it to a member of another opposing team (different from the team from which they received it), repeating the process described in Rule 2.
5. *Round Structure:* During each round, the ball must be passed to players of all four teams (groups).
6. *Event Selection:* Events already classified are no longer available as options.
7. *Winning the Game:* The team with the highest accumulated

points at the end of the game is declared the winner.

D. Active Experimentation

The game's dynamic nature enabled children to experiment with their understanding of probabilistic concepts in real-time. The gameplay encouraged strategic thinking, adaptability, and collaborative problem-solving. By applying new or acquired knowledge to classify events, and justifying their reasoning, children are, actively engaged, in testing their learning within a practical, dynamic, and competitive environment.

IV. RESULTS

The qualitative analysis of this exploratory study focused on children's interactions, and researchers' field notes, revealed significant insights into the development of probabilistic thinking in a non-formal learning context, as detailed below.

During the initial phase, when discussing examples of "certain" and "impossible" events, children provided arguments for their understanding of these concepts. For instance, one participant identified "the sun rising tomorrow" as a certain event, while "raining every day" was categorized by another participant as impossible. The initial individual discussions revealed their ability to identify events at the extremes of the probability spectrum and justify their reasoning logically.

In creating the "Event Sheet", one group debated whether the outcome of flipping a coin ("heads or tails") was "equally likely" or "more likely" compared to another event, such as "drawing a ball from a certain color" of a bag containing balls of three distinct colors, distributed unevenly. This revealed an evolution in probabilistic thinking, showing that participants have begun to understand some nuances of relative probabilities.

During the game, one participant classified the event "it will rain tomorrow" as "very likely", based on her knowledge of the

local weather forecast (mobile phone access to the local weather forecast). However, another group member argued that without knowing any weather information (data), the event should be classified as "equally likely." This exchange of arguments between group mates shows how the interactive format encourages critical thinking by making participants critically evaluate their assumptions, justify their classifications more clearly and objectively, and consider the reliability of the information they used.

When creating the Paper Fortune Tellers, one participant initially numbered the faces sequentially, while another suggested using random numbers to ensure a higher degree of randomness. This exchange of ideas between peers contributed to establishing a deeper understanding of the concepts of randomness.

These examples illustrate how a non-formal learning environment, based on an active, dynamic, and collaborative methodology rooted in Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, can effectively promote the development of critical, creative, logical, and probabilistic thinking in children aged 10 to 13 years old.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This exploratory research provided valuable insights into the development of probabilistic thinking in children within a non-formal learning environment. Based on Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, the study demonstrated how a game-based methodology can promote understanding and engagement with abstract and complex concepts, such as probabilistic concepts.

Integrating all four stages of Kolb's learning cycle in a game-based learning approach, led to a deep involvement of the participants. Structured activities, from creating fortune tellers to participating in a serious game, provided children with opportunities to experiment, reflect, conceptualize, and apply probabilistic reasoning in meaningful contexts.

The activities allowed children to explore and internalize key probabilistic concepts such as "impossible," "certain," "likely," "equally/more/less likely," and "unlikely." The group discussions and collaborative classification tasks provided a platform for critical thinking, enabling participants to clarify their understanding and justify their reasoning. This progression was particularly evident in their ability to distinguish between relative probabilities, as demonstrated during debates on scenarios like flipping a coin or drawing colored balls from an uneven distribution.

The collaborative nature of the activities was a key factor in promoting peer-to-peer learning. Group discussions encouraged children to articulate their thoughts, challenge assumptions, and refine their reasoning through constructive oral communication. The role of group leaders further highlighted the importance of responsibility, and teamwork in achieving shared goals, as leaders encouraged constructive discussions and maintained accurate game records.

The gameplay environment emphasized real-time decision-making and adaptability. Participants testified their ability to deepen and apply learned concepts when classifying events and providing justifications under time constraints. The game

environment stimulated active participation and fostered strategic thinking and critical reasoning skills.

The informal and engaging structure of the summer school session proved to be highly effective in supporting children's learning. The non-traditional setting removed pressures often associated with formal education, allowing children to explore concepts freely and interact with their peers in a supportive environment.

This study underscores the potential of non-formal learning environments to complement formal education, particularly in introducing and reinforcing abstract concepts like the probability ones. The success of the interactive and collaborative methodology suggests that similar approaches could be applied to other mathematical and scientific knowledge areas. Future research could expand on this work, investigating the long-term impact of such methodology on children's cognitive development; exploring its application and adjustments to distinct age groups or educational contexts; and incorporating more advanced probabilistic scenarios to, further, challenge participants, and deepen their understanding. The findings of this study reaffirm the value of experiential and active learning in enhancing conceptual understanding and critical thinking. By engaging children in collaborative and meaningful activities, the adopted methodology promoted the development of probabilistic reasoning and fostered cognitive, emotional, and social skills. This research highlights the transformative potential of non-formal education when thoughtfully designed to align with well-established learning theories, offering a promising direction for future educational innovation.

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